

Risk Aversion and Women Empowerment

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ABSTRACT

Empowering women means equipping them with the means to participate in virtually every sphere of existence, economically as well, without encumbrances. It has been concluded by several researchers that women are usually more conservative in taking risks as compared to men, a variation which is in most instances explained in relation to the socialisation processes that discourage risk-taking behaviours in girls while encouraging them in boys. This research seeks to investigate how risk aversion affects the financial decision-making of women from different age cohorts focusing on the role of self-confidence and empowerment in investment decisions. The results show that women aged 45 years and below are more risk averse than older women above 45 years. However, the young woman is more aggressive in taking on such financial risks and, importantly, has to be exposed to a much wider range of investments. The research was carried on between mothers and their daughters, and data were collected via Google Forms that were later analysed through descriptive statistical methods.

Keywords: *Risk Aversion, Empowerment, Financial instrument, Confidence level*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Women Empowerment

Empowerment for women is strengthening women to take on the world in all ways even financially. Empowering women is the prime step for the progress of the country. Why is it that there is just a small number of women who are being empowered and not all of them. Unempowered women are not able to progress in life, the empowered ones are changing their way of life, they are progressing so well. Empowering women has made them strong enough to make their own decisions and stand up for themselves and for the right.

Risk aversion for women empowerment is a no go. Women empowerment plays a very important role in upgrading the financial levels of an economy. Women are believed to be such great economists specially for the households because of the way they manage the finances mainly when they look after the areas of expenditure. Studies have also shown that the women joining the C-Suite companies have tended to become less risk-averse (Palmquist, 2016). This is a direct result of empowering women. Women are more risk averse. The fear of incurring a loss holds them back from taking big risks that even if has less chances but still does of working out. Empowering women is a game changer for all the financial decisions one would make.

1.2 Risk Aversion

Risk aversion in its simplest meaning would state the risk involved in making financial investments. It has been shown in past research that women are highly risk-averse. High-risk aversion is not good for bringing women up front in the economy. Risk aversion tends to be a barrier to taking forward the ideals of women's empowerment. A risk-averse person would generally prefer a lower return with a lesser number and known risks rather than higher returns with unknown risks. Risk aversion is a factor holding back the growth of both men and women. Empowering both men and women lowers their tendency to be averse to risk.

Being risk-averse creates a visible barrier between you and unwavering success. From a business point of view, being risk-averse is not the right thing. Believing that risks would bring a negative impact is wrong. Taking risks would make life more interesting. It can be very beneficial to take a big risk, there are always equal chances. Risk aversion may look appealing to an individual in the short run but it might be very profitable for a team in any business in the long run as it leads people to irrationally avoid good opportunities.

1.3 Understanding Risk Aversion

Risk aversion is an extremely important concept in the world of behavioral economics and finance. It is basically how individuals are more inclined to take the road of lesser risk to avoid failure, especially in dicey and uncertain conditions. The risk aversion level includes elements, that can vary from one individual to the other and can be affected by numerous things such as a person's personality, past experiences, the background of a certain culture, and economic status. In economic terms, people with a high aversion to risk typically opt for the stable and secure approach at the expense of potentially higher returns, even if the odds for success are high. This careful strategy might prevent the rise, and sometimes, the development of specific operations that help grow businesses, investment decisions, and career development.

1.4 Risk Aversion in Women

Studies consistently show that, as a rule, women present higher risk aversion than men do. This variability is often due to the gender-socialization processes which lead girls to be more risk averse while boys are the opposite (Filippin, 2016). The mere existence of cultural norms and societal norms is itself a huge factor in shaping this behavior. The fact that women are often confined to seeing the family's future as the most important element they should be working on might be the very reason they adopt taking risks more conservatively. The problem is that this attitude is the very source of failure to achieve women occupying leading positions and getting involved in entrepreneurship.

When it comes to financial decisions, women express their risk aversion in various ways. They may inspect huge, well-carefully chosen, and low-risk investing options, they would also be more careful in terms of business deals, and they would try to steer clear of high-stakes financial transactions. Even if it can be a little worn down by conservatism and leads to potential losses, a conservative approach may still provide an effective tool for risk-aversion in commoditizing sectors, especially where the schoolgirl is so afraid of being outed from company management or the writer from being so wrong in his conclusion paragraph. Furthermore, the judgment of risks may be additionally controlled by men's attitudes and stereotypes that may multiply the cycle of women's risk aversion.

1.5 Risk Aversion in Indian Women

Here the problem of risk aversion for Indian women is pictured as a product of the patriarchal power hierarchies that are so typical of many Indian regions which not only discourage women from doing so but In many Indian regions, the misogynist nature of the places forces this caste to propagate the stereotype that then perpetuates itself. Thus, asset-financed, two-dimensional access to financing and knowledge aside, it has resulted in the parasite of risk aversion in Indian women, whoever is unfortunate not to have them. Yet, it should be ascertained that this phenomenon is not homogenous in all the areas and the subcultures are there. For example, in feminist societies, such as in some locations of India, e.g. Meghalaya,

diverse money usage models could be presented, and women have a more significant role in finance management.

1.6 Risk Aversion Across Generations of Indian Women

Through various other trends, the emergence of risk aversion amongst Indian women also incarnated intergenerational, influenced by the changing social situation, increasing wealth acquisition, and enhanced access to studies and a wide range of jobs. Earlier Indian women were more risk-averse in comparison due to the more restrictive cultural norms and scarcity, and this pattern of behavior is more common among people who fall into the older demographic brackets and grew up in traditional settings. This is mainly due to the societal norms and limited opportunities that defined their formative years.

But looking at the difference in approach to the issue among the younger women, particularly the ones who are more educated and overshadowed by the globalist wave, it becomes clear that they are forming a new norm. They are now displaying an entrepreneurial nature, taking center stage in the labor market and at the same time comfortably making more daring monetary decisions. Nevertheless, the impact of civilians still overlays the pressure of family and society and the enormity of the challenges. This is in addition to the existing structural barriers in the economy, which lessen women's participation.

Through this transition, it is emphasized that it has become even more important to keep the momentum of economies of scale through financial education and strategic empowerment of women. The presence of normalizing barriers where women across all generations are capacitated to defy the odds by addressing the core risk-aversion facilitates malpractices which in turn leads to them being full participants in the economy and society.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Aim

This study aims to explore the generational differences in financial risk tolerance among women, focusing on the relationship between confidence, financial empowerment, and risk aversion. By comparing the financial decision-making behaviors of women across two sets of generations namely above 45 and below 45 this research seeks to understand how risk aversion influences financial empowerment across generations.

2.2 Data Collection

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed via online platforms. The questionnaire included both closed and open-ended questions about financial decision-making, investment preferences, risk tolerance, and confidence in financial matters. Participants were approximately 50 mothers and daughters across various generations, ensuring diverse representation. The survey was designed to minimize biases and was distributed widely to ensure broad participation from different socio-economic backgrounds.

2.3 Data Analysis

The analysis included looking for patterns and trends within the financial behaviors of respondents, once data was collected. The first step was to clean and tidy the data, which included removing all incomplete records or non-relevant answers. Next, we performed descriptive statistics to characterize trends in financial decision-making by the mothers and daughters.

Statistical Techniques were used to address the research questions. The relation between confidence levels, which refer to the extent to which a person believes in his or her ability to choose more risky financial alternatives, and willingness to risk-taking behavior was explored, henceforth it is examined if higher levels of confidence among individuals entail innate behavior towards being receptive with their finances.

2.4 Ethical Considerations

Important ethical considerations were built into the research design and carried out. The focus of the study was to ensure respectful and confidential care for every participant from its inception. Participants were made aware of the purpose and rights accorded to them as human subjects in this research, such as they could report anytime without any harm. This is hopefully not too difficult to grasp, the survey was built with only what research purposes of the project in mind, and no personal identifiers were included inside of that data set.

All the participants were given informed consent obtained after they completed the questionnaire. The respondents were informed that their responses would not be revealed and would only serve academic needs. The data was stored securely and only the research team had access to it. The study followed the ethical guidelines for academic research throughout all experiments, respecting participants' rights and dignity.

The results from this research will be given in a way that safeguards the anonymity of respondents, as outputted to add to academic learning about risk aversion and women's empowerment through financial decision-making. Abiding by these ethical guidelines, research is expected to produce valid and reliable findings that can ultimately inform future studies and policy efforts within the emerging sector.

2.5 Demography

Figure 1: Education Qualification of the Respondents

Figure 2: Percentage of annual income saved by the respondents

Figure 3: Distribution of average age of respondents

Figure 4: Occupation of the respondents

Figure 1 talks about the educational qualification of the respondents where it is clearly seen that almost 50 percent of the respondents are postgraduates and about 25 percent have professional qualifications. Figure 2 summarises the different percentages of annual income saved by these respondents and it can be inferred that almost 53 percent of these women save more than 15% of their annual income. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the average age of the respondents where the maximum number of women aged between 42 to 53 years. Figure 4 shows what occupation these women are in almost 66 percent of women are in the service sector and about 22 percent are in business

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Awareness of Financial Instruments

Table 1: Average of awareness scale for Financial Instruments among women below and above 45 years of age

	Risky	Non-Risky
below 45	6.66	4
above 45	5.66	3.29

As shown in Table 1 women under 45 show greater awareness of a wider variety of financial instruments compared to older women. They are more inclined towards exploring riskier investments than the non riskier ones.

Women under 45 demonstrated a greater awareness of a wider variety of financial instruments compared to older women. In support of this trend, Nelson (2012) explored differences in risk preferences by gender and found that younger females are more exposed to a diverse range of financial products because of improvements in both financial knowledge and access. Younger women also tend to involve themselves more significantly with riskier instruments like stocks and mutual funds, while the older group is confined mainly to the more traditional and low-risk ones, such as fixed deposits and bonds. Moreover, a study by Holden and Tilahun (2022) supports this, revealing that younger women, particularly those with better access to education and economic resources, display higher financial literacy, enabling them to diversify their investments into riskier categories such as equities and cryptocurrencies.

3.2 Preference for Risky vs. Non-Risky Investments

Table 2: Average of the scale of preference for Financial Instruments among women below and above 45 years of age

	Risky	Non-Risky
below 45	28.33	18.53
above 45	24.91	13.5

As also shown in Table 2 younger women displayed a stronger preference for risky investments compared to older women, though both groups prefer a balance between risk and safety in their portfolios.

More risk is preferred in investment portfolios by women than by older women. According to Duflo, research proved that younger women are currently becoming more comfortable with the idea of taking risks during financial decisions, remarking that the empowerment through financial independence of younger women plays a crucial role in this regard (Duflo, 2012). Duflo (2012) argues that as women gain economic autonomy, they tend to shift from conservative financial instruments to those with higher returns, such as stocks and mutual funds. This reflects your findings, where women below 45 were more willing to explore high-risk investments, while older women preferred safer, more stable options

3.3 Primary objective when making financial investments

Table 3: Primary objective of making Financial Investments among women of below and above 45 years of age

	Below 45	Above 45
To assure the safety of principal amount	4.2	4.5
To generate income	4.0	4.1
To achieve a	4.1	3.6

particular investment goal		
To accumulate assets for retirement	3.5	4.1
To reduce income tax	3.7	3.1
For financial stability	4.4	3.8
Retained earnings	4.1	3.6
Contingency planning	3.5	3.0
To gain knowledge	2.6	2.9

The study also highlights a difference in investment priorities between younger and older women. While younger women with a 4.0-degree preference focused more on generating income, 4.4 degrees for achieving financial stability, and 3.5 degrees for contingency planning, older women with 4.5 degrees prioritized the safety of their principal amount and 4.1 degrees for retirement accumulation. This is consistent with the conclusions of Rink and Barros (2021), who found that younger women are more likely to invest with the goal of income generation and wealth accumulation, reflecting their higher confidence in managing complex financial portfolios. In contrast, older women are typically more risk-averse and emphasize security in their investment decisions, mirroring your findings.

3.4 Agreement and preference over pair of investment types

Table 4: *Agreement and Acceptance over various pairs of investment types among women of below and above 45 years of age*

	Below 45	Above 45
I Prefer FD’s, RD’s, PPFs etc over securities offered by the Stock market	3.7	4
I Prefer Preference funds over Equity funds	3.1	2.8
I Prefer Debt funds over Preference funds	2.3	2.8
I Prefer Real estate investment instead of Stock exchange	2.9	3

I Prefer Gold investment instead of Bonds or Debt funds	3.7	4.2
I Prefer investment in Mutual funds or SIP instead of a single investment	3.6	3.2
I Prefer investment in Governments Bonds instead of Private investment	3.1	3.1
I Prefer Insurance over SIP funds	2.7	2
I Prefer investment in MCX instead of Equity/ Preference	2.0	1.7
I Prefer investment in Equity Funds instead of Convertible funds	2.8	2.1

Women's investment preferences differ in numerous ways depending on the age of the woman in question, and especially so with respect to age groups below and above 45 years respectively. Women within the age bracket of 45 and below go against the general trend of women's investing behavior by being more willing to put their money in the stock market than those above 45 who would be satisfied with fixed deposit accounts and the like. This observation is supported by a study conducted by Rink and Barros (2021), which highlighted similar trends where younger women, especially those more educated and financially empowered, tend to favor riskier and higher-return investments. Furthermore, Duflo (2012) points out that older women are generally more conservative in their investment strategies, preferring lower-risk assets such as fixed-income securities). These findings reinforce the generational gap in financial decision-making, where younger women are increasingly taking bold steps in their investment choices. The younger, as well as the older category, do not show any great aversion to investing in preference funds rather than equity funds, although younger women tend to indulge in equities a bit more than their older counterparts. In the case of investing in debt funds, older-generation women are more inclined to such options than younger-generation women, who tend to do the opposite. Within real estate investments, however, both groups experience a similar moderate level of interest choosing it over investing in stock exchanges. It is worth noting that women above 45 years tend to buy more gold as younger women do not engage in such a tendency. Mutual funds or SIPs are preferred by both groups over single investments, with younger women showing a slightly higher curiosity. Women of all ages are more likely to choose government bonds than any private investments. They also prefer seeking the former group of funds rather than insurance for younger women, who also happen to be below 45 years while the opposite is true with older women in particular those above 45 years and above. Interestingly enough, the age difference

does not seem to impact the investment experience in MCX amongst women. In the end, younger women are more inclined towards equity funds as a mode of investment, although their tendency towards convertible funds is almost at par with that of older women.

This preference for riskier investments by younger women indicates a broader shift towards financial independence and empowerment, as documented by studies such as Holden and Tilahun (2022), who observed that younger women are less constrained by traditional financial norms and more willing to engage in modern financial markets.

4. CONCLUSION

This research highlights the critical role of addressing risk aversion in women as a key factor in financial empowerment. While younger women are becoming more confident in taking financial risks, there is still a long way to go in breaking down the societal norms that inhibit women from fully participating in the financial sector. Financial education and empowerment programs that target women across generations can help reduce risk aversion and promote more equitable participation in the economy. These findings align with existing literature, particularly the work of Nelson (2012) and Rink and Barros (2021), which also emphasize the importance of financial education in helping women overcome risk aversion. By reducing these barriers and encouraging more proactive financial decision-making across generations, we can foster greater gender equality in the financial sector.

REFERENCES

- Duflo, E. (2012). Women empowerment and economic development. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 50(4), 1051–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.50.4.1051>
- Holden, S. T., & Tilahun, M. (2022). Are risk preferences explaining gender differences in investment behaviour? *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*, 101, 101949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2022.101949>
- Nelson, J. A. (2012). Are women really more risk-averse than men? In *Global Development and Environment Institute*(No. 12–05). Tufts University. <https://www.bu.edu/eci/files/2020/01/12-05NelsonRiskAverse.pdf>
- Rink, U., & Barros, L. (2021). Spending or saving? Female empowerment and financial decisions in a matrilineal society. *World Development*, 141, 105342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105342>
- Times of India Blog*. (2022, November 16). Women's empowerment in India, from ancient period to modern time period. *Times of India*. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/scatteredthoughts/womens-empowerment-in-india-from-ancient-period-to-modern-time-period-46689/>

World Vision Australia. (n.d.). Women's empowerment - facts, stories and how to help. *World Vision Australia*. <https://www.worldvision.com.au/womens-empowerment>

Filippin, A. (2016). Gender differences in risk attitudes. *IZA World of Labor*.
<https://doi.org/10.15185/izawol.100>

Palmquist, M. (2016, December 15). *Female CEOs: A steady hand at the wheel*.
Strategy+Business.

<https://www.strategy-business.com/blog/Female-CEOs-A-Steady-Hand-at-the-Wheel>